

ENCOURAGING INNOVATIVE THINKING THROUGH DIGITIZATION OF EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

In the present competitive world Education in the right direction shape the future of the students. The demographic dividend which India has right now can be exploited through providing education in right direction. Affordability and accessibility of education in India is addressed through Reservations and Acts like Right to Education. But because of Colonial masters, India is mastered in education system where memorizing things and collecting factual information play important role. The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) in 2014 had ranked India 66 out of 140 countries in terms of local dynamics of innovation. This shows very dismal picture of the Indian education system. Added to this the NASSCOM – Mckinsey report “Perspective 2020: transform business, transform India” (2009) said only 26% of India’s engineering graduates were employable. This shows the lack of opportunities created by Indian education in the classrooms because of lack of infrastructure facilities namely digital modes. We have in our research paper conducted experiment explaining the concept of Inflation by employing black board and combining explanation and points, pictures and animated videos. We have taken fifty students and asked the solution to overcome the problem of Inflation, in situation without using digital tools we have succeeded in clarifying the concept but failed to build the more imagination and creativity in them for longer period. Finally we conclude that digital teaching will enhance or stimulate creativity among the students and successful in clearing the concepts.

Keywords: Education, Affordability, Development, Creativity and Innovation.

Objectives:

Objectives of the paper are as follows:

1. To see the various loopholes in Indian Education system,
2. To see how effective is digitization in Education system,
3. To find out various bottlenecks in effective utilization of digitization in Education.

Research Methodology of the Study:

This study is based on experiment conducted in the college selecting randomly fifty students as participants and secondary source of data through research papers, magazines and newspapers. By looking into experiment results and secondary data we have analyzed and concluded.

Introduction:

India is young nation in the sense that share of its youth in total population in 2011 stands at around 35%. This human potential can be efficiently utilized by way of encouraging creativity

and innovative minds in the students. Innovative ideas should be nurtured in schools and colleges, for that we should create environment in such a way that which encourages students to some creative works. Schools and colleges should have infrastructure facilities attached with committed teaching staff. In modern competitive world we have to create innovative minds for that latest available technologies should be adopted like digital technology. Primarily Digital Education has 3 components: content, technology platforms, delivery infrastructure ^[1]. Therefore we need to focus on the content, platform and infrastructure then only effective education can be delivered through the digital mode.

In this research paper to find out the impact of teaching backed by digital tools on their skills we have conducted an experiment taking fifty students. First we taught the economic concept Inflation through chalk and talk way to randomly selected fifty students and then the same fifty members were taught through smart board using digital tools that is projector using animated teaching on inflation. We have asked the question that how to overcome the problem of Inflation before and after digital teaching. The students have answered more comprehensively during the teaching backed by digital tools. This is because they have imagined clearly with the help of animated one and answered well. With the overall analysis we have come to the conclusion that digital way of teaching has more positive impact and encourages creativity by way of clarifying the concepts well through pictures and animations.

Negative sides of our Education System:

Indian traditional education system was focused more on practicality like Guru Kula type of education system. That was followed by the British education system which focused more on British interest than intellectual improvement among the Indians. This education system made students only for remembering the information only. There are number of negative aspect in our education system that totally kills creativity and interest among the children.

The diagram clearly shows that present education system focuses mainly on the memorizing the things that will ultimately leads to creative thinking, interest and encouragement from students

taking back seat. This education system does not provide security to our students as far as employability is considered. This was supported by some study on higher education last year estimated that fewer than 15% of graduates with Master’s Degree were employable.

Therefore we should create a education system that encourages creative skill, encourage innovation etc. The INFO-TAINMENT

combination involved in digital education makes it more practical, applicable and relatable to our life and surroundings in an interesting manner ^[2]. The need of the hour is to encourage digital education for our students to compete with the competitive global world.

Results and Discussion:

Digital Education can be defined as the use of a combination of technology, digital content and instruction in the education system to make it more effective and efficient than the traditional

education system [3]. The adopted digital technology should be tuned in such a way that should ensure the local needs. To know the impact of the digital education on the students we have conducted the experiment in our college by randomly selecting students.

In our college C.G.Bellad GFGC Akkialur, Hangal (Tq), Haveri (Dt), Karnataka, have conducted an experiment related to the impact of the Digital education on creativity and understanding of the concepts. For this we have taken economic concept called Inflation, and randomly selected fifty students. Initially we have taught the inflation with chalk and talk method, explained the concept clearly. This method clearly explained the concept, but here unable to touch their imagination that much; this was assessed by the questions posed on them.

The concept selected was Inflation, in chalk and talk the concept explained clearly but same content explained with the digital tools viz. smart board, projector etc. in the traditional method explanation backed with examples but in the digital teaching we have included pictures, animations etc. After teaching we posed a question that how to overcome the problem of inflation? The Answer by the same students was recorded. The answer to the question contains both supply side and demand side answers, but more concept clarity was needed to answer to imagine the supply side answers. We have listed their response in percent form.

Table 1: Showing Answer by the students in each mode of teaching

Mode of Teaching	Answers	
	Demand Side Answers	Supply side Answers
Chalk and Talk	99%	1%
Digital Teaching	45%	55%

When we analyze the responses collected we could easily find out that education through digital tools yielded better results compared to the chalk and talk method. In the traditional method of teaching we make students to imagine but in the digital teaching through the pictures and animations their imaginations are directed in the desired direction and creative thinking can be influenced.

We have also listed the level of interaction by the students before and after concept clarity through digital mode. That is the quality of answers given by the students when questions about Inflation posed in various angles. The overall effect of the digital education is charted out in the bar diagram in the below.

Fig 1: Showing the level of quality answers by the students

When we clearly analyzed level of quality answers after and before Digital teaching we could see that the level of quality answers increased much in the digital teaching. We have divided the quality of answers into three categories i.e. below level, average level and higher level based on the closeness of the answers to the reality. We have recorded the quality answers given by the students and put in the bar diagram which clearly indicates

that the level of interaction and quality answers were improved. This shows the positive impact of the Digital education on the students by stimulating the interest and creative skills among the students.

Findings from the experiments:

The key in developing the effectiveness of digital learning on teaching lies in teachers ^[4]. The success of the any mode of education system depends on the teachers, take for instance even digital education also needs human face to tune ethics and morality in to the education system. We have come across with some interesting findings while doing this experiment with digital mode; they are as follows

- ✓ Digital teaching with the help of figures, pictures and animation will stimulate interest among the students,
- ✓ The digital education will encourage creative thinking among the students by way of shaping the imagination in the right direction,
- ✓ It involves active participation by the students because of understanding made easy,
- ✓ Difficult concept can easily be explained through the digital mode of teaching,
- ✓ Repetition can also be made easy, quick assessment can be done through this processes,
- ✓ Understanding abilities of the students can be easily identified through the digital education process,
- ✓ This process makes students to remember the concepts longer time, because of the usage of pictures and animations etc.
- ✓ Easy updating can be made through the digital education because it is easy to update the current information in PPT's and newly developed animations can be easily included.

Challenges we face to go digital education:

We have listed above the various positive side of the digital education, but there are many negative side of digital education for its implementation. They are as follows:

- ✓ Teachers' should have minim technical mind in handling the digital education tools,
- ✓ There should be a balance between talk and animation,
- ✓ Rigorous training should be given to the teaching community,
- ✓ We should update ourselves regularly,
- ✓ Government's initiatives needed for the effective digital education in the country,
- ✓ Operating cost is high that is acting as the obstacle for the implementation of digital education in the country,
- ✓ Maintaining the balance between students, teachers and technology should be there, the right mix of them will yield better results,
- ✓ Educational institutions in the village level will face some kind of obstacle because of their availability of digital education delivery facilities.

These are the some of the important problems of that comes in the way of implementing the digital education.

Conclusion:

The present competitive world provide platform to those who have creative thinking and innovative minds. The necessary facilities should be provided to the young India to exhibit their

talent, one among them is to provide education through the digital mode. The education should reach everybody that can easily achieve through the digital education. The right to Education is rightly achieved through digital education because the digital education not only ensures equity but also affordability. Right content and method of delivery in the digital education will ensure creative thinking, innovative mind and interest among the students.

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